

ENHANCING VOCABULARY ACQUISITION THROUGH CORPUS-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL MODEL IN ESL CONTEXTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19160728>

Abstract:

The article investigates the role of corpus-based approach in the enhancement of vocabulary development in ESL contexts. It examines theoretical foundations of vocabulary acquisition and highlights the pedagogical potential of corpus linguistics in language learning.

Keywords: vocabulary acquisition, lexical competence, corpus, Skell, autonomy.

In the age of globalization, language education has been transformed significantly because of the widespread use of digital resources in classrooms. The shift from conventional techniques to Corpus-based teaching emerged due to various difficulties like accurate word selection for conveying thoughts, restricted understanding of word definitions in translation, and the difficulty in the memorization of information by learning words via lists. The aim of the article is to examine the theoretical foundation of corpus-based vocabulary instruction and highlight its practice potential by proposing integrated activities with Sketch Engine for the lexical development in EFL contexts among learners.

Education has to follow main trends like pursuing the use of technology and online platforms for improving students' vocabulary acquisition along with the opportunity to observe the incorporation of digital tools in classrooms. Referring to the article of Aguial Garcia, the author proposes that the definition of "vocabulary acquisition" is the procedure of receiving and interpreting ideas with the help of learned words. [Aguial Garcia ML, 2024:117] Theoretical views from various linguistic schools offer diverse interpretations of vocabulary growth. Building on the concepts of Jean Piaget, Rajkumar and Malini contend that language advancement takes place via engagement with the environmental context. This perspective holds that learners enhance their vocabulary learning through active involvement in meaningful situations instead of simply memorizing terms passively. [Malini & Rajkumar, 2019] As we can see, vocabulary acquisition might be interpreted as the observation of real-life situations, which enhance the process of mastering language. These theoretical interpretations indicate that vocabulary learning is a complex cognitive and social process. As defined by Richard Nordquist, lexical competence refers to the ability to understand and appropriately use words in communication. It encompasses knowledge of meaning, form, collocation, register, and pragmatic usage. [Nordquist, 2024]. Therefore, lexical competence can be viewed as a cognitive process that enables learners to perceive, interpret, and appropriately use vocabulary in communication.

The growing reliance on digital gadgets among learners can potentially demonstrate benevolent consequences. Over the past three decades, Corpora and CL approaches have been dedicated to systematic language learning by providing empirical data, frequency and pattern based approaches. The notion of a "corpus" was offered by Eric Friginal describes a corpus as an organized electronic compilation of authentic language data. Such collections include authentic written or spoken texts systematically compiled and analyzed to identify, enabling researchers to examine usage trends across genres and registers. [Eric Friginal, 2017:12] Modern corpora such as COCA, BNC, and SKELL provide user-friendly interfaces for pedagogical

purposes. In the present study, SKELL (Sketch Engine for Language Learning) is selected due to its accessibility and educational orientation.

Moving to the practical part of study, several tasks will be presented with the incorporation of SKELL. In "Corpus in Focus: A Guide to Use Corpus in EFL/ESL Classroom", the author proposes tasks that are oriented on the improvement of vocabulary development. [Abdulrahim, 2023: 48]

Activity 1. Word Clouds: The objective of this activity is to expand thematic vocabulary and explore semantic associations. Students enter a target word into SKELL and analyze the generated word cloud displaying frequent collocates and related terms. For instance: Freedom has close-related words like right, liberty, independence, peace, ability and others.

Activity 2. Word Matching: Students might use a corpus or authentic texts to match lexicon with their meaning and use them in real-life situations, leading to the improvement of reading and writing skills. To clarify the point, learners might explore the word "issue" and find Word Sketch such as address issue, resolve issue, tackle the issue.

By exposing students to day-to-day examples of collocations, frequency, and contextual meanings, it first enhances their lexical awareness and accuracy. Students take an active role in their education by utilizing programs like SKELL. They explore word patterns and concordance lines while gaining independence and analytical abilities. However, it is important to take into account some limitations such as the interpretation of linguistic data and require additional time, so it can be challenging for novices.

In conclusion, corpus-based instruction represents an effective and innovative methodology for enhancing vocabulary acquisition within ESL contexts. It stimulates a more profound understanding of lexical items, facilitates long-term retention, and encourages learner autonomy through the utilization of authentic language data. Hence, the integration of corpus tools into EFL classrooms has the potential to substantially enhance lexical competence and promote meaningful language use in both academic and real-life communication.

References:

1. Abdulrahim, A. (2023, April 24). *Corpus in Focus: A guide to use corpus in EFL/ESL classroom*. Proceedings of the International Summer School of Bilingualism and Multilingualism (ISSBM2022). <https://books.ung.si/issbm2022/chapter/abdulkadir-abdulrahim-corpus-in-focus-a-guide-to-use-corpus-in-turkish-efl-classroom/>
2. Aguilar García ML (2024). Vocabulary acquisition in the language classroom: what it is, how it works, which strategies and approaches are suitable for Latin instruction. *The Journal of Classics Teaching* 25, 116–122. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S2058631024000059>
3. Friginal, E. (2018). Corpus linguistics for English teachers. *New tools, online resources, and classroom activities*, 30.
4. Malini, K., & Rajkumar, R. (2019). The Role of Cognition in Learning the English Language.
5. Nordquist, Richard. (2024, June 25). Lexical Competence. Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-lexical-competence-1691114>